

Structural analysis of the new Bioactive Kinetic Screw in titanium alloy vs. commercially pure titanium

Carlos Aurelio Andreucci¹, Elza M. M. Fonseca², Renato N. Jorge³

¹ PhD Engenharia Biomédica, FEUP | Faculdade de Engenharia do Porto; candreucci@hotmail.com; Porto; Portugal

² LAETA, INEGI, Mechanical Engineering Department, School of Engineering, Polytechnic Institute of Porto; elz@isep.ipp.pt; Porto; Portugal

³ LAETA, INEGI, Mechanical Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto; ; rnatal@fe.up.pt; Porto; Portugal

Abstract

This study presents the structural and static analysis of the new Bioactive Kinetic Screw (BKS) using the finite element method (FEM). The FEM was conducted to predict three-dimensional (3D) simulations according to a cutting torque applied at a constant feed rate. The results were compared using two different materials in the BKS simulation: commercially pure titanium (cp-Ti) and titanium alloy (typically Ti6Al4V). BKS modelling was done in Solidworks[®] and the FEM analysis was performed in the ANSYS Workbench 2020 R2[®] software. According to the results, it was observed that the low imposed cutting torque and BKS in cp-Ti material are recommended to obtain a less effective stress in the screw. In addition, the low imposed cutting torque and BKS in Ti6Al4V material are recommended to obtain less equivalent strain and total deformation level in the screw.

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1. Introduction

Drilling is the most used process to produce holes, and it is essential for different industries and clinical medical centers [1]. To minimize time and costs of the experimental tests of the cutting process, before use, computer models have become more numerous, providing accurate and safe conditions [2]. Many researchers have developed analytical, numerical, and experimental tests to predict and control different drilling parameters [1-7].

Numerical methods based on the finite element analysis (FEA) are widely used presenting many advantages compared to other methodologies, due the reduction of the cost, to avoid wasting time during analysis, as well as faster designer of any component [8]. This method allows finding the approximation solution of partial differential equations of analysis due to the boundary conditions imposed on the problem.

FEA is extensively used in many fields, originally developed for numerical solutions of complex problems in solid mechanics [9]. FEA has been recognized as a crucial solution to a variety of structural, modal, fatigue, thermal, fluid, or electromagnetic design problems. Nowadays, different range of purposes are applied in all these domains, namely in implantology [10].

FEA can simulate the interaction between the implant and the surrounding bone. Some different studies allow the identification of load transfer at the bone-implant interface, which depends on the type of load, material properties, geometry (diameter, shape, length), among other characteristics [10].

Different studies have been focused on optimizing the implant geometry to provide the favorable stress level for different static or dynamic conditions of applied load, due the interaction between the implant and the surrounding bone [10].

For dental implants a range of different material have been recommended [10-13]. Typical materials used are: Pure Ti (cp-Ti), Ti6Al4V, Type 3 gold alloy, Ag-Pd alloy, Co-Cr alloy and Porcelain, [10, 12-13]. In the most reported studies, the materials are assumed to be homogeneous, linear and have elastic materials characterized by Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio [10, 12-13].

In the present study, commercially pure titanium (cp-Ti) and titanium alloy (typically Ti6Al4V) were chosen for the analysis of the new BKS. Titanium dental implants can offer many advantages. They have excellent characteristics, namely excellent corrosion resistance, passivation capacity and biocompatibility [11-14]. According to investigations by

Shah et al. [11] concluded that, under experimental conditions, cp-Ti and Ti6Al4V provide similar osseointegration and biomechanical anchorage. Furthermore, the authors concluded that machined surfaces exhibit similar morphology, topography, phase composition and chemistry [11]. The choice of implant materials can greatly affect the stress concentrations at the implant-bone interface that is still under discussion [10].

Different authors have been studied the effect of the drilling force and torque as important parameters to avoid overloading the bone tissue [14]. Another important parameter is related with the bone temperature caused by the drilling. According to the study by Alam et al. [14] the decrease in bone temperature was attributed to the reduced time required for the drill to penetrate the bone, as a function of the drill rotation speed. In all experiments, the authors used a range between 600 to 3000 rpm for the drilling speed with constant feed rate [14]. According to a protocol, established by the research from Mihali et al. [15], for reducing the drilling sequence during implant preparation, based on temperature and insertion torque, the mean torque that the authors have been applied to all bone densities was a range between 44.12 and 45.04 Ncm, with a rotational speed of 800 rpm.

In this work, to analysis and measure the drill resistance capacity as a function of the applied torque, a 3D finite element model of the new BKS (at 4mm in diameter and 10 mm in length) was tested using two materials: titanium alloy Ti6Al4V (Grade 5) and commercially pure titanium cp-Ti (Grade 4). This new BKS presents itself a new delivery system for the use of natural growth factors, since the characteristic is to introduce protein molecules, cells, blood, and particulate bone through the hole of the BKS by a system of drill flutes; it also becomes a new means of delivering growth factor in surgery for expansion, lifting and bone fixation [16]. The main objective of this work was to identify the values of the cutting torque that must be applied in the BKS, depending on the rotational speed between 2250 to 4000 rpm, so that the ultimate strength of the material is not exceeded. The torque value is of great importance, since high values in the drilling can cause the drill breakage during the surgical incision [12, 17].

2. Material and Methods

In this research work, a 3D numerical and structural linear model was developed using ANSYS 2020 R2[®] - Workbench 2020 R2, with the new BKS biomechanism in Ti6Al4V (Grade 5) and commercially pure titanium cp-Ti (Grade 4). The mechanical properties of the materials used in the study are shown in Table 1.

Ti6Al4V Grade 5 alloy is the most commercially available of all titanium alloys. Widely applied to medical and biomedical implants, it offers an excellent combination of strength and toughness, corrosion resistance, good weld, and manufacturing characteristics.

Cp-Ti Grade 4 is an unalloyed titanium, with excellent corrosion resistance, good weld, high strength, and used in different types of industries.

Table 1 – Mechanical properties [11, 18].

	Ti6Al4V (Grade 5)	cp-Ti (Grade 4)
Young's Modulus, GPa	114	105
Poisson's Ratio	0.36	0.32
Ultimate Tensile Strength, MPa	896	553
Tensile Yield Strength, MPa	827	483

The numerical model aims to simulate the drilling process of the BKS biomechanism and evaluate the distribution of mechanical stresses and strains in the screw material. The 3D model was built using Solidworks[®] and ANSYS 2020 R2[®] - Workbench 2020 R2 software, as shown in Fig.1.

Boundary conditions, which represent typical drilling phenomena, are established on the lower surface of the BKS as fixed, and on the upper surface with the application of torque, Fig.1(a). Based on the geometrical model, volumetric finite element meshes were generated using SOLID187. SOLID187 element is a higher order, defined by 10 nodes having three degrees of freedom at each node (translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions), Fig.1(b). This tetrahedron element has a quadratic displacement behaviour with four-point integration and is suitable for modelling irregular meshes, such as those produced from various CAD/CAM systems [19]. The simulations are based on Lagrangian finite element model performed to determine the effective stress and strain.

Fig.1 – BKS model, static structural analysis (ANSYS 2020 R2 ® - Workbench 202 R2). (a) Boundary conditions. (b) Mesh.

In the present study, an electric motor EM-12L with a maximum power of 59 W was selected, and angular speeds between 100 and 40000 rpm [20].

The new BKS tool, intended for use in ongoing research, will work with different angular speeds depending on the material of which it is made, and with a constant feed rate of 0.5 mm/sec vertically downwards. In this study, only the mechanical load due to the cutting torque M_t was considered in the model and the thermal effect produced by the BKS was not considered in this simulation.

The relation between the torque (M_t in Nm), the maximum electrical power during drilling (P in W) and the speed of rotation (n in rpm) is determined according by Eq. (1) [19].

$$M_t = 9.55 \frac{P}{n} \tag{1}$$

3. Results and Discussion

In the present study, six numerical simulations were performed, varying the cutting torque according to the imposed and appropriated rotational speed for each BKS tool material, Table 2.

Numerical results of stress, strain and deformation level were obtained during the structural analysis on the BKS for different imposed cutting torques, according to the rotational speed from 2250 to 4000 rpm. The chosen drilling parameters were due to the obtained values for the ultimate tensile strength in the BKS, identified for an imposed rotational speed higher than 2250 rpm, as presented in Table 2. The obtained values of the cutting torque decrease with the increase of the rotational speed.

Table 2 – Drilling parameters.

Tool BKS	Power derived from cutting torque, Ref: Electric Motor EM-12L [20], P=59 W	
	Cutting torque, M_t Ncm	Rotational speed, n rpm
Ti6Al4V (Grade 5)	25.04	2250
	22.54	2500
	18.78	3000
cp-Ti (Grade 4)	17.34	3250
	16.10	3500
	14.09	4000

Before the simulations, different mesh convergence tests were performed, where the computational error was minimized by changing the number of elements, as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 – Different mesh convergence. Number of elements in (a) 18175 (b) 18857 (c) 23215 (d) 76105.

Convergence tests were performed by changing the number of elements to obtain the maximum stress values verified at the tip of the BKS model and compared with the ultimate tensile strength of the material. As shown in Fig.3, in four solutions, the stress values converge where the smallest percent error obtained was 4.3% using 23215 finite elements. To obtain a finite element accuracy criterion of mesh discretization, an error smaller than 7% must be considered [8]. Accordingly, the mesh adopted to use in our simulations consists of a total of 23215 tetrahedron elements, Fig.2(c).

Fig.3 – Mesh convergence and error (e).

The obtained results from the total deformation, equivalent elastic strain, and equivalent stress for BKS allow us to conclude on the drilling parameters chosen for each BKS material. The results are shown for each different applied cutting torque on BKS and presented in different figures. Figs.4 to 9 represent the results for each material of the BKS, as a function of the applied cutting torque.

Fig.4 – Equivalent stress in BKS with two materials. (a) Ti6Al4V (Grade 5). (b) Cp-Ti (Grade 4).

Fig.5 – Maximum value of equivalent stress in BKS model for all drilling parameters.

Fig.6 – Equivalent elastic strain in BKS with two materials. (a) Ti6Al4V (Grade 5). (b) Cp-Ti (Grade 4).

Fig.7 – Maximum value of equivalent elastic strain in BKS model for all drilling parameters.

Fig.8 – Total deformation in BKS with two materials. (a) Ti6Al4V (Grade 5). (b) Cp-Ti (Grade 4).

Fig.9 – Maximum value of total deformation in BKS model for all drilling parameters.

Numerical results show that stress, strain, and deformation levels tend to increase with lower BKS rotation or higher imposed cutting torque. At the tip of the screw, the BKS presents higher stress and strain. The deformation is closer to the imposed cutting torque. The equivalent elastic strain determines the level of equivalent stress in the BKS that can be transmitted to the drilling process in bone material.

The calculated strains and stresses vary along the entire length of the BKS, and this can be justified by the inertia of its cross-section, due to the existing space in the BKS mechanism. The inertia cross-section at the bottom decreases and the stress increases.

The maximum stress, strain and deformation values are verified when a cutting torque equal to 25.04 Ncm is applied, corresponding to the minimum rotational speed of 2250 rpm. Comparing the materials, the high level of stress, strain and deformation is produced when the BKS is Ti6Al4V material.

The BKS mechanism achieves greater deformation, stress and elastic strain for high cutting torques at low speed. The BKS in cp-Ti material presents the lower values of stress and strain, since that the material strength is lower than Ti6Al4V. The screw with less stress will allow for a longer tool life, as mentioned in the literature [21].

4. Conclusions

In the present study, numerical simulations were performed implementing a 3D FEM model. A total of 6 simulations were performed to study the effect of cutting torque and screw material on the drilling process. The BKS is in Ti6Al4V or cp-Ti material of 4 mm diameter. The drilling process uses different rotational speeds. The chosen drilling parameters were due to the obtained values for the ultimate tensile strength in the BKS for each material. This study can be used to avoid the difficulties that normally occur during the drilling process.

The described simulation demonstrates that the screw causing strains, stresses, and deformations during the imposed cutting torque, which can affect the bone. Based on the simulation results, the low cutting torque imposed on the BKS on cp-Ti material is recommended to obtain lower stress levels on the screw. The screw with lowest stress will have a longer tool life.

The BKS mechanism achieves higher stresses for high cutting torques at low speed and in Ti6Al4V material.

The new BKS presented for dental drilling presents a space in the mechanism that can be occupied by particulate bone, resulting in the accumulation of material removed inside the implant screw.

As future research, BKS can be analysed to improve its life cycle, more tests can be performed to estimate the maintenance time of BKS replacement, more tests can be performed to combine BKS in bone material and verify the interaction and accumulation of material inside the screw.

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